

GENOMED4ALL

D2.5

Recommendations on the ethical principles, quality processes and stakeholder engagements for AI development

GENOMED4ALL

Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

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Authors	Nathan Lea (i~HD), Dipak Kalra (i~HD), Francesco di Tano (UNIBO)
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Abstract

Deliverable 2.5 summarizes the proposed ethical principles for GenoMed4All and wider multi omics and clinical data driven projects for rare diseases that involve the training and development of risk prediction and outcome measure algorithms that leverage artificial intelligence.

D2.5 goes on to describe the approaches for stakeholder engagement (including clinical practitioners and sites, development teams, AI researchers and patient associations and the

wider citizenry). This includes quality processes derived from the ethical principles where consideration of the ethical challenges around autonomy, bias and transparency in data use amongst others are pertinent.

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Table of contents

1	Executive summary	8
2	Introduction.....	9
2.1	Deliverable Structure	9
2.2	What is the ALTAI Key Requirements?	10
2.3	Who are the Stakeholders?	10
3	Exploring the Key Requirements, Ethical Principles and ALTAI Assessment	13
3.1	Human Agency and Oversight.....	13
3.2	Technical Robustness and Safety	14
3.3	Privacy and Governance	15
3.4	Transparency	16
3.5	Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness.....	17
3.6	Environmental and Societal Well-Being	18
3.7	Accountability.....	19
4	ALTAI Assessment Framework Responses.....	20
4.1	Review of Responses to ALTAI Web Toolkit for Requirement 1: Human Agency and Oversight 21	
4.2	Review of Responses to ALTAI Web Toolkit for Requirement 2: Technical Robustness and Safety 22	
4.3	Review of Responses to ALTAI Web Toolkit for Requirement 3: Privacy and Governance	26
4.4	Review of Responses to ALTAI Web Toolkit Requirement 4: Transparency	29
4.5	Review of Responses to ALTAI Web Toolkit Requirement 5: Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness.....	32
4.6	Review of Responses to ALTAI Web Toolkit for Requirement 6: Environmental and Societal Well-Being.....	38
4.7	Review of Responses to ALTAI Web Toolkit for Requirement 7: Accountability	41
5	Ethical Principles, Quality Processes, Stakeholder Engagements and Discussion ...	45
5.1	Recommended Ethical Principles	45
5.2	Stakeholder Engagement and Quality Processes.....	47
5.3	Discussion.....	49
6	Conclusions	51

List of figures

Figure 1: ALTAI Introductory Section	20
Figure 2: Technical Robustness and Safety ALTAI Responses (Page 1)	22
Figure 3: Technical Robustness and Safety ALTAI Responses (Page 2)	23
Figure 4: Technical Robustness and Safety ALTAI Responses (Page 3)	24
Figure 5: Technical Robustness and Safety ALTAI Responses (Page 4)	25
Figure 6: Privacy and Data Governance Altai Responses (Page 1).....	27
Figure 7: Privacy and Data Governance Altai Responses (Page 2).....	28
Figure 8: Transparency ALTAI Responses (Page 1).....	29
Figure 9: Transparency ALTAI Responses (Page 2).....	30
Figure 10: Transparency ALTAI Responses (Page 3).....	31
Figure 11: Responses to ALTAI Requirement 5 - Discrimination and Fairness (Page 1)	32
Figure 12: Responses to ALTAI Requirement 5 - Discrimination and Fairness (Page 2)	33
Figure 13: Responses to ALTAI Requirement 5 - Discrimination and Fairness (Page 3)	34
Figure 14: Responses to ALTAI Requirement 5 - Discrimination and Fairness (Page 4)	35
Figure 15: Responses to ALTAI Requirement 5 - Discrimination and Fairness (Page 5)	36
Figure 16: Responses to ALTAI Requirement 5 - Discrimination and Fairness (Page 6)	37
Figure 17: ALTAI Responses to Environmental and Societal Wellbeing (Page 1)	38
Figure 18: ALTAI Responses to Environmental and Societal Wellbeing (Page 2)	39
Figure 19: ALTAI Responses to Environmental and Societal Wellbeing (Page 3)	40
Figure 20: ALTAI Responses for Accountability (Page 1)	41
Figure 21: ALTAI Responses for Accountability (Page 2)	42
Figure 22: ALTAI Responses for Accountability (Page 3)	43

List of tables

Table 1: Stakeholder Engagement Recommendations 49

Abbreviations

HDs	Haematological diseases
FL	Federated Learning
NN	Neural Network
MDS	Myelodysplastic Syndromes
MM	Multiple Myeloma
SCD	Sickle Cell Disease
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy AI
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
JCA	Joint Controller Agreement
REC	Research Ethics Committee
IRB	Independent Review Board

1 Executive summary

Deliverable 2.5 describes the ethical principles for GenoMed4All and similar AI driven projects and interventions for managing and risk assessing rare Haematological diseases. This description of principles draws from the European Commission Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence.

The Guidelines prescribe seven key requirements to establish trustworthiness for AI and a further Assessment List for Trustworthy AI to measure adherence. This Deliverable assesses against a Pilot Version of the ALTAI – an assessment framework which has been in development by the European Union and has in early 2024 been published as a pilot Web Based Tool and just in time for this Deliverable.

A full assessment is attached as supplementary PDFs to this Deliverable. Commentary on the implications of the assessment is also provided. The principles contained in this deliverable are designed to assert these requirements as assessed against the ALTAI.

In addition to the ethical principles D2.5 provides details of quality processes associated with the ethical requirements as well as guidance on stakeholder engagement when developing AI. The quality processes are handled in line with the ALTAI assessments and the stakeholder engagements focus on how the Project has engaged with its main stakeholders, including clinical professionals, data providers, rare disease researchers, developers and the wider citizenry.

D2.5 discusses these main points and concludes with commentary on the sustainability of GenoMed4All and implications for other AI driven research programmes designed to improve health outcomes and citizen health self-management.

The Deliverable will be reviewed by the GenoMed4All Ethical Advisory Board and will be publicly shared for additional comment an assessment by similar projects and programmes. A consideration of AI Act compliance and impact is also provided.

2 Introduction

Deliverable 2.5 describes the ethical principles and stakeholder engagement for GenoMed4All and similar AI driven projects and interventions for managing and risk assessing rare Haematological diseases. This description of principles draws from the European Commission Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence¹. The Guidelines prescribe seven key requirements to establish trustworthiness for AI and a further Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI)² to measure adherence. The principles provided in this deliverable are designed to assert these requirements and allow for the effective evaluation against the ALTAI. The Deliverable describes the assessment GenoMed4All has made against the ALTAI when considering the operation of the project since 2021 and the ethical principles that have been developed from it.

2.1 Deliverable Structure

This Deliverable assesses explicitly against the ALTAI – an assessment framework has been in development by the European Union and has only recently in early 2024 been published as a pilot web-based tool for assessment³, just in time for this Deliverable. D2.5 therefore makes a general consideration of the principles against the ALTAI as well as a full assessment using the pilot web-based tool.

This introductory section outlines the approach taken to develop the guidelines and assessments, key requirements and the stakeholders with whom GenoMed4All has worked, describing their apparent and more general likely priorities for the requirements. Section 3 provides an exploration of the seven requirements for Trustworthy AI and their implications for GenoMed4All. Section 4 presents the responses to the ALTAI assessment toolkit with a discussion of the responses. Section 5 provides the ethical principles that have been developed on consideration of the ALTAI and GenoMed4All's experience, offering a discussion of stakeholder engagement and the use of existing quality processes to consider any future trials that will need to be set up for the GenoMed4All solutions to be sustainable. A discussion of the results, their limitations and implications and consideration of AI Act compliance are also provided in Section 5.

D2.5 concludes with a discussion of the principles and their development, with recommendations for their wider use. It reflects on the journey taken to develop the principles and the challenges that the development of AI and its impact on research and the wider citizenry, which GenoMed4All will help steer its sustainability and the activities of similar projects in the AI driven innovation space for health. A consideration of the likely readiness for the AI Act compliance is also provided.

¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

² <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment>

³ <https://altai.insight-centre.org>

2.2 What is the ALTAI Key Requirements?

The seven key requirements derived from the Ethics Guidelines which substantiate the ALTAI are as follows:

1. human agency and oversight
2. technical robustness and safety
3. privacy and data governance
4. transparency
5. diversity, non-discrimination and fairness
6. environmental and societal well-being and
7. accountability

In developing the principles for GenoMed4All, WP2 has reviewed and interpreted these seven requirements to frame their relevance to GenoMed4All. Additionally, the reasons for focusing on these requirements are to ensure that the principles can be readily interpreted and operationalised as appropriate and have been further scrutinised by a self-assessment of the project against the ALTAI. These requirements

2.3 Who are the Stakeholders?

GenoMed4All has brought together a network of expertise and for its delivery and has engaged wider stakeholders in its work. The expertise and stakeholders are described here, as well as the contribution to this project and a treatise on their likely priorities for the ALTAI requirements.

Clinical Researchers and Practitioners (Haematological Diseases): GenoMed4All has worked with a series of clinical researchers who may or may not have direct point of care responsibilities. In either case, their activities are central to understanding the nature of the diseases that GenoMed4All is focused in. This expertise also covers key concerns around the availability and utility of data, its interpretation and the basis upon which design and training choices should be made for the algorithms that are being developed for risk predication and diagnostics. Their ongoing contribution to understanding the scientific research challenges and engagement with developers and their teams has been critical for developing the project and its outputs. This has also been vital for wider public engagement and understanding in terms of transparency and understanding wider impacts of the project as well as its appropriate governance. They are also keenly interested on how any proposed interventions might work in their usual workflow, and how much control they retain in terms of understanding recommendations from AI and how they are implemented in practice.

Infrastructure Operators: In developing software services and high performance computing networks, infrastructure providers are key in terms of being able to implement and deploy the AI driven services and ensuring that security and infrastructure are robust. The providers are not only those who are responsible for any project specific central servers, but also those who are

employed and operate within the data provider infrastructure in a federated learning environment. It is these stakeholders who will need to be able to respond. To the security, governance and system robustness considerations within the ALTAI as well as certifications for existing and forthcoming regulations as they move forward. Certainly the robustness, safety, environmental and accountability aspects are key assessment points.

Designers, Analysts and Developers for algorithm training and software services: this group of stakeholders are pivotal in terms of the engineering, data analyses and implementation of the algorithms and their surrounding systems. Between them they need to analyse and interpret the data in line with clinical researchers, specify the training models, interpret the statistical modelling and ensure that the software services are properly developed and deployed on functional infrastructure. They too will be held accountable for the quality, governance transparency and robustness aspects of the ALTAI and are pivotal in achieving a solid assessment and assurance around the algorithm uses.

Programme Managers and Internal Oversight: In terms of running a development project like GenoMed4All, this relies on ensuring that all stakeholders are adequately communicating and updated about their activities as well as reaching of milestones. This is a particularly complex process in terms of the number of partners in a consortium like GenoMed4All, as well as the complex nature of the diseases that it is addressing and the technology it using to do so. The formation of an independent ethical advisory board is key to ensure that there is some ongoing independent oversight of the project as a whole, and independent provision of sustainability advice also assists with this. Their activities are paramount to ensure that the accountability and fairness aspects of the ALTAI are being upheld.

Regulators and Commissioners: This group of stakeholders operate outside of the consortium partnership but are of course keenly interested in its success and delivery. These range from Research Ethics Committees and regulatory teams across the partners, all the way through to the commissioners of the project and its sponsors. From an ALTAI perspective, a key element will be around regulatory compliance and transparency as well as societal impacts, but they will be keenly concerned with existing regulatory compliance.

Patients, Research Participants and the Wider Citizenry: Arguably the key stakeholder, the engagement and views of the public are critical in terms of not only maximising the utility of the AI interventions as they are built, but also to ensure that they remain positive about digital interventions more generally and engaged in their own health concerns. They are also the key “litmus test” for the assessment of transparency concerns, as well as the wider accountability from an ALTAI perspective. The key areas however are likely to be around the agency and oversight of algorithm operation – either via understanding of who or what is providing their care from a human or an AI system, or both, and what the scope of activity, autonomy and control is for either. All seven requirements from the ALTAI however will be points of key concern for citizens. From a

research participant perspective, their focus will be on the execution of the research project aspects for GenoMed4All and an interest in the findings and future impacts for society.

3 Exploring the Key Requirements, Ethical Principles and ALTAI Assessment

This section explores the seven key ALTAI requirements provided by the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence that GenoMed4All has developed. Each subsection discusses a requirement, including its ramifications for GenoMed4All and the preparation for the responses to the APTAI toolkit which are provided in Section 4, and the development of the principles GenoMed4All has derived provided in Section 5.

3.1 Human Agency and Oversight

Human agency and oversight impact key stakeholders in GenoMed4All. This relates to the research participants whose data is being processed actively and freely allowing it to be used (including in cases where it may be anonymous) and their being able to oversee the point and purpose of its use via transparency and clearly understood information leaflets and outreach.

Agency and oversight also extend to clinical professionals who are actively engaged with GenoMed4All in an advisory and guidance capacity as putative future users of risk prediction modelling and use in practice. The ability for medical and research professionals to be able to interpret and control information and its interpretation is a fundamental concern when using autonomous systems to interact and guide interpretations and interventions.

GenoMed4All has followed an approach whereby the outputs of the trained algorithms relate to risk prediction and diagnostics can be interpreted and questioned by any clinical user of the system, and to be explained to patients directly. By avoiding black box approaches, GenoMed4All's philosophy remains to allow scrutiny to be applied to any findings and recommendations whilst ensuring that the training can be achieved with clinical oversight.

Agency and oversight of key stakeholders is especially important when it comes to GenoMed4All's goals around networking larger scale omics datasets and federated learning. The decisions to incorporate larger datasets and train the algorithms is key to ethical principles around data reuse, as well as human knowledge and understanding of the data sets that have been used to train the algorithms. This is especially the case for the developers of the neural networks and directed learning approaches for the AI.

The research and development teams must therefore ensure that they are able to effectively understand and interpret the data used so that they can oversee the appropriate guidance and assessment of the algorithms as they develop. This is also the case for the network developers and infrastructure custodians – a matter more for the technical robustness of the solution.

Human Agency and Oversight remains a key matter of concern to regulatory and legal teams, ethicists and regulators. From the GenoMed4All experience, the ability to ensure that humans remain in control suggests that for the acquisition through to the processing of the data and thereafter the interpretation of results, the participant, clinical and research teams must be able to handle the data and have a clear say in how it needs to be used and interpreted knowingly and willingly.

Moving forward, as the solutions are developed and use in practice as well as for research, the challenge will be to ensure that agency and oversight continues to be respected, including in the application of the algorithms in practice or through research to better profile the disease areas where the interpretation of the algorithms can be assessed and accepted or rejected, with all findings and pathways that are unlocked being explored and scrutinised openly and transparently.

The ethical principles below are explored in more detail in the Stakeholder Engagement section 4.

3.2 Technical Robustness and Safety

The development of infrastructure to support federated learning at scale is complex and requires effective interoperability between data sources, access APIs, algorithm training and results management. This entails effective and robust network connection and establishment of zones of control from data providers to data users.

The data flows and risk management for GenoMed4All has been covered in D2.1 and D2.2 in detail. GenoMed4All has worked to ensure that each of the technical teams understand the architecture and the data management processes and components so that they can effectively communicate and process a variety of data sources to train the algorithms.

The Project also took an early view that federated learning should be the primary focus and that centralising data sets should be minimised to manage security and data protection risks. To that end the management and implementation of data exposure to algorithms running in data provider sites had to be established.

The design choices have been documented and the risk mitigation strategies have therefore been documented to demonstrate a clear basis upon which robustness can be measured and safety can be assured – at least from the training perspective. For a live service that is safety critical, different service level agreements and assurance mechanisms are needed from an operational perspective.

With regards the accuracy of the AI tooling operation, GenoMed4All like any sensitive data reliant programme needs to have some sense of the quality of the data to inform the assessment of the safety of the algorithms and their effective training. This applies a complexity in the assurance of

safety because there are several points where accuracy of the data relies on its quality and the processing of that data to inform the algorithms needs to be assured. This relies on the data providers being able to assure the quality of the data upon which algorithms are trained, and the developers of the algorithms to be able to assure the quality of their processes for their training. This in turn requires that the processing is transparent and that the learning and reaction of the algorithms can be explained. This is also picked up in the Transparency Requirement 5.

In any event, the overall system architecture will need to balance safety considerations and robustness with minimising data movement that may be neither optimal or necessary. Whilst many platforms operate with duplicated components, data sets and resources to effect a clear ability to rapidly transfer to backup systems and processes, this level of redundancy may itself pose a challenge for high performance computing and safety critical systems. The assurance of data quality and the operation of the algorithms poses further core requirements to meet the ALTAI requirements in real terms, as we describe in the next section.

3.3 Privacy and Governance

Adherence to privacy and confidentiality requirements is at the core of any endeavour that involves the reuse of data collected during health care interventions. Coupled with the requirements for adhering to research governance standards the approach used by GenoMed4All to establish the data governance frameworks and by default the privacy requirements. Full details of this can be found in D2.1 and D2.2 as well as D10.5, D10.7, D10.8, D10.9 and D10.10 which each describe the data protection and risk management approaches, assurances for lawful and legal bases for GenoMed4All to function, The Data Protection Impact Assessments latest draft, the codes of practice and the Data Management Plan.

The approach has taken a Data Protection by Design and Default approach to assess the data protection and associated compliance risks as described in GDPR. From an early stage, data protection and privacy considerations have informed and driven the governance approaches that in turn have guided the design and development choices across the development and data management teams and have informed the educational outreach.

A key decision for the project was to limit the centralisation of data relating to citizens and patients, whether it was identifiable, anonymous or pseudonymised. All clinical, imaging and omics data would remain in the data providers' control and infrastructure, and the machine learning and algorithm development would occur remotely in the data providers' sites.

The model adopted by GenoMed4All has been a Federated Learning Model, where the only data sharing is that of statistical analyses on the source data that defines the models that in turn inform the machine learning. Privacy risks have therefore been mitigated to a degree by limiting the exposure of data to those who already have access to them. It also means that only the machine

learning processes are permitted access to the data and any troubleshooting or explanations can be made in collaboration with data providers who already have access to the data.

The Federated Learning Model also means that the provisions for security can be consolidated at the data provider infrastructure and the risk of data breaches and leaks can be more closely mitigated there. Adding data to a central repository can enhance these risks and requires additional security.

The governance of GenoMed4All in terms of access can also be more effectively implemented using the Federated model. Existing procedures and practices can continue to be managed by each of the sites whilst a central management becomes less complex since on the statistical models need to be shared. This gives sites an opportunity to review their own procedures whilst keeping in line with GenoMed4All's existing governance approach. This approach aligns with GDPR and requires data processing proposals to be reviewed via a DPIA at project and at site level, where these changes can be addressed in terms of organisational risk management processes.

The signing of Joint Controller Agreements (JCA) also specifies the baseline governance and security requirements that need to be provided by each partner whether they are providers and / or recipients of data. This establishes consistency in the development and implementation of the algorithm design and data processing, and it ensures that all parties to the agreements understand their roles as Joint Controllers of data and that even running machine learning remotely still constitutes personal data processing and the need for governance to match this requirement even if recipients don't themselves see the data.

This is a key point for privacy preservation and governance ethical principles and stakeholder understanding around roles and responsibilities for protecting data. It is vital that contracting party stakeholders understand their GDPR responsibilities as early as possible to ensure that contracts can be drafted readily, and amendments can be minimal – legal teams and departments are assiduous and can take time to respond to drafts so as much must be done make clear the governance frameworks as clearly and unambiguously as possible.

3.4 Transparency

Transparency around data use, practices and activity are a cornerstone of ethical and effective data processing activity. Its importance for AI governance and assurance is even more critical not only to provide assurance and demonstrate trustworthiness to the citizenry, but also because it is now a requirement for high risk systems in the recently established AI Act for which GenoMed4All's results would certainly fall under.

To that end the importance of ensuring that not only appropriate consents have been sought for any existing or prospective data collection, but also that this has been effectively overseen by

independent Research Ethics Committees (RECs) or Independent Review Boards (IRBs). The reason that this is so important is that it is a sanity check to ensure that the expression of data handling and use is clear and understandable and reaches a standard for research participation. The wording of consent forms is vital to ensure the lawful participation in research and that participants fully understand what is involved. These should form part of information leaflets for participants and reflect how data is processed.

The role of RECs and IRBs however must also be carefully considered. The experience of GenoMed4All and other research projects is that there can be inconsistency across different RECs both within national jurisdictions and across different countries and their respective committees. This matter is addressed under Section 3.6 in more detail but must be noted here.

These information points are vital to achieve the quality of transparency that is expected by not only an ethical consideration of the use of AI and its development, but also compliance with the AI Act itself. Traditional approaches for participant recruitment can and must inform the standards for transparency around AI.

GenoMed4All fully recommends the reuse of its materials around transparency not only for the sustainability of the project, but also for any AI interventional tool that is developed. The principles that GenoMed4All offers below provide a framework to guide the development.

Template transparency materials for the project have been published as part of the WP10 deliverables. This approach has been vital for transparency requirements as handed down by GDPR. Whilst the AI Act goes some way to enforce the need for clear transparency about the development of AI, there is an element of uncertainty as to how well it will enforce any intervention that is not deemed high risk or clarify requirements for those that are. GenoMed4All therefore offers these materials as cases in point to be read and reused with the following ethical principles.

3.5 Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness

The conditions that GenoMed4All has focussed on are rare and represent a population that arguably cannot be best served due to limits of data availability and outcome measures. GenoMed4All was developed based on being able to improve this situation by leveraging data sources for machine learning more readily and in combination with projects like SYNTHEMA⁴ the use of synthetic data is being explored to ensure that this lack of data can be improved using AI to provide more inferencing and data for model training.

GenoMed4All has therefore had to address issues around diversity, non-discrimination and fairness where the balance to be struck between ethical and awful access to data must be balanced with ensuring that an already disadvantaged group is not further disadvantaged by

⁴ <https://synthema.eu>

compromising the ability for them to enjoy the benefits of cutting edge technology, risk prediction and support for their disease management.

To that end the Federated Learning Model has been pivotal in allowing use of as much data as possible without significant risk to privacy protection and ethical concerns. In the case of GenoMed4All, it is arguable that the risk of lack of equity is greater in the MM, MDS and SCD cases in the sense that there could be a denial of access to new services and treatment techniques as opposed to not receiving the benefits, recognition or considerations from the development of new systems as it might in a larger disease cohort.

Additionally from a fairness perspective, as discussed in section 3.4, inconsistencies with how ethics committees review proposals and take an inconsistent view must be considered carefully. Arguments may need to be made around fairness and consistency when opinions are gathered but this situation does run the risk of inadvertent discrimination impacting detrimentally on one cohort over another.

3.6 Environmental and Societal Well-Being

The primary concerns around environmental and societal factors poses an interesting challenge for health care delivery and research. As largely safety critical systems, the need to ensure that robust physical infrastructure is available to run the high performance computing networks necessary to support AI algorithm processing is clear for healthcare delivery.

The challenge from the environmental perspective is largely related to costs and environmental impacts of electricity and supply for the data centres and computing infrastructure that house these facilities. The costs of power supply have hurred due to several factors and concerns around carbon offset and impact on the environment has compelled the funders, commissioners and the owners of these services to limit the availability of infrastructure to only what is necessary.

From the research perspective, the availability of the infrastructure does not hold quite the same urgency as clinical interventions might. The work of GenoMed4All has not yet reviewed its impact on the environmental factors given that it may be harder to isolate the GenoMed4All's impact on carbon emissions and power usage but if trialled and deployed for assessment and ultimately use in care, it would adopt a similar safety critical component as any other trial or clinical intervention.

From the wider societal impact, the ALTAI focuses on the impacts on humans in the sense of their employment and prospects for their won skills which may be replaced by the AI provision. GenoMed4All as a potential risk prediction and diagnostic intervention process does not remove human oversight or involvement in these areas and furthermore will require the same if not enhanced human skills to understand, interpret and apply the recommendations moving forward. To that end GenoMed4All only anticipates a positive enrichment of human activity, not its replacement.

3.7 Accountability

Accountability around the development of any health intervention tool is a cornerstone of most regulatory and governance processes. GenoMed4All has adopted an approach to governance grounded in the requirements of GDPR, as well as expectations around medical device assessment and HTA requirements.

This has stood the project in good stead to be able to demonstrate high assurance around its ability to be held accountable as far as the ALTAI assessment is concerned.

The accountability responses therefore remain relatively clear and the broader discussions around development traceability and audited by third parties.

4 ALTAI Assessment Framework Responses

Section 4 a summary of the ALTAI Assessment Results and their implications, which are attached as supplementary PDFs for review and embedded in this document as Figures 1 – 22. Figure 1 provides an introductory paragraph and set of notes to the assessment.

Please note also that the ALTAI Toolkit tool challenges assessors to specify their views on the adequacy of their solutions to meet the requirements. This is a self assessment which in the case of this Deliverable should be understood as a basis to instruct further development and trialling of the GenoMed4All tools.

Figure 1: ALTAI Introductory Section

4.1 Review of Responses to ALTAI Web Toolkit for Requirement 1: Human Agency and Oversight

Please refer to the PDF titled “Human agency and oversight - GenoMed4All ALTAI Assessment – ALTAI” for a full specification of the responses Figure 2. GenoMed4All has endeavoured to ensure that overreliance on AI, manipulation of user behaviour is limited and ensuring that human intervention remains part of the equation.

Whilst most of the measures that have been taken as described above appear to have been adequate for the context of assessing the feasibility of an AI driven tool, GenoMed4All has had limited opportunity to address user manipulation. This is partly because the trialling of any products is beyond the scope of the project.

In considering sustainability, GenoMed4All has started to consider what a pre-clinical trial might look like and the extent to which the ALTAI needs to be considered in that context. The Deliverable recommends that impacts on user behaviour need to be considered as part of an interventional trial and assessed according to user experience practices. The process flow of when the AI tooling will be deployed and used in the trial and treatment setting must be very clearly defined so that the impacts of the AI intervention can be fairly and fully assessed. This approach will provide the basis for developing submissions to Health Technology Assessment (HTA) bureaus as we all demonstration to appropriate competent authorities for the forthcoming AI Act compliance needs for high risk AI systems.

4.2 Review of Responses to ALTAI Web Toolkit for Requirement 2: Technical Robustness and Safety

Figures 2 – 5 below provide the ALTAI Responses for Requirement 2.

The screenshot shows the ALTAI web toolkit interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, How To Complete The ALTAI, Fundamental Rights, My ALTAs (highlighted), Hello nathan.lea@i-hd.eu!, and Logout. The main content area is titled 'ALTAI for GenoMed4All ALTAI Assessment' and includes a 'Notes' button and a 'Sections of the ALTAI' sidebar with categories like Human Agency and Oversight, Technical Robustness and Safety (selected), Privacy and Data Governance, Transparency, Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness, Societal and Environmental Well-being, and Accountability. Below the sidebar is a 'Legend of progression symbols' and 'Resources' section. The main content area is titled 'Technical Robustness and Safety' and contains a paragraph explaining the importance of dependability and resilience. It then lists four questions with radio button options:

- Is the AI system certified for cybersecurity (e.g., the certification scheme created by the [Cybersecurity Act in Europe](#)) or is it compliant with specific security standards? Yes No Don't know
- How exposed is the AI system to cyber-attacks? * Exposed To some extent Not exposed Don't know
- Did you assess potential forms of attacks to which the AI system could be vulnerable? Yes No
- Did you consider different types of vulnerabilities and potential entry points for attacks such as: * Data poisoning (i.e., manipulation of the training data) Model evasion (i.e., classify the data according to the attacker will) Model inversion (i.e., infer the model parameters) Other
- Did you put measures in place to ensure the integrity, robustness and overall security of the AI system against potential attacks over its lifecycle? Yes No

Figure 2: Technical Robustness and Safety ALTAI Responses (Page 1)

Please describe the measures

The approach has taken a federated learning model where the security of the systems remains in the control of the data providers within their own established information security management systems where they reach a high level of compliance given the they are health care providers or academic institutions.

Did you red-team/pen test the system? *

Yes
 No
 Don't know

Do you inform end-users of the duration of security coverage and updates? *

Yes
 No
 Don't know

How long is the expected timeframe within which you will provide security updates for your system? *

This remains in the control of each site that need to conduct its own periodic checks. All sites have signed a Joint Controller Agreement to reach baseline security and information requirements. Individual audits can be performed if necessary.

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the resilience to attacks of the AI system? *

Non-existent Low Moderate Significant High

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the measures you have adopted to ensure resilience? *

Non-existent Completely inadequate Almost adequate Adequate Fully adequate

Figure 3: Technical Robustness and Safety ALTAI Responses (Page 2)

General Safety

Could the AI system have adversarial, critical or damaging effects (e.g., to human or societal safety) in case of risks or threats such as design or technical faults, defects, outages, attacks, misuse, inappropriate or malicious use? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Accuracy

Could a low level of accuracy of the AI system have critical, adversarial or damaging consequences? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you put in place measures to ensure that the data (including training data) used to develop the AI system is up to date, of high quality, complete and representative of the environment the system will be deployed in? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you put in place a series of steps to monitor, and document the AI system's accuracy? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you consider whether the AI system's operation can invalidate the data or assumptions it was trained on, and how this might lead to adversarial effects (e.g. biased estimators, echo chambers etc.)? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Did you put processes in place to ensure that the level of accuracy of the AI system to be expected by end-users and/or subjects is properly communicated? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the risk that the AI system's accuracy drops below intended level? *

- Non-existent
- Low
- Moderate
- Significant
- High

How would you rate the measures you have adopted to ensure system accuracy? *

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

Figure 4: Technical Robustness and Safety ALTAI Responses (Page 3)

Reliability, fall-back plans and reproducibility

Could the **AI system** cause critical, adversarial or damaging consequences (e.g., pertaining to human safety) in case of low reliability and/or reproducibility? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Is your **AI system** using **online continual learning**? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the reliability of the **AI system**? *

- Non-existent
- Low
- Moderate
- Significant
- High

How would you rate the measures you have adopted to ensure system reliability? *

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the reproducibility of the **AI system**? *

- Non-existent
- Low
- Moderate
- Significant
- High

How would you rate the measures you have adopted to ensure system reproducibility? *

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the fall-back you have adopted? *

- Non-existent
- Completely inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

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Figure 5: Technical Robustness and Safety ALTAI Responses (Page 4)

In considering the ALTAI questions for Requirement 2, the responses that were made indicated that risks were significant but that the framework for compliance allowed for each partner to assess their risks and liabilities effectively. An assessment of the proposed DEDALUS infrastructure and CINECA operations formed the main part of the oversight and allowed for some assurance to be developed at a project wide level.

In addition to the assessments the partners also entered into a Joint Controller Agreement as outlined in D2.2. In this agreement, provisions and undertakings around information security were made, including around security management, access controls, antivirus updates and firewall configurations.

Whilst GenoMed4All has not yet sought to audit compliance with the agreements, this Deliverable notes that assessment of approaches and security management via the ALTAI suggest that such a review or audit should be commissioned, and that the compliance assessed according to that framework. A result of this exercise might be to assess against activities such as Penetration Testing and measures put in place around resilience and disaster recovery.

This would need to be handled alongside the assessments of data quality and the processing of that data to develop meaningful and fair algorithms that can demonstrably provide accurate results. This relies on transparency and explainability of those processes.

4.3 Review of Responses to ALTAI Web Toolkit for Requirement 3: Privacy and Governance

Please see the ALTAI responses for Requirement 3 in Figures 6 – 7.

The ALTAI responses for privacy and data governance were more readily assured for GenoMed4All. Through the seeking of independent ethical review as well as the activities of the GenoMed4All Ethical Advisory Board, the core rights to privacy, physical, mental and moral integrity as well as data protection could be justified, along with the flagging of key issues around equity, representation and fairness. Additionally the governance framework provided a basis to assure compliance with GDPR.

The right to consent and withdraw has been addressed via the governing frameworks of the retrospective and prospective data collection, the alignment with standards such as ISO 27001 and the ongoing assessments and developments of the solutions within a trial setting for future view have ensured that the data lifecycle and its protection is considered as the AI is developed. This is highlighted in the establishment of the following principles.

The screenshot shows the 'ALTAI for GenoMed4All' assessment interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Home', 'How To Complete The ALTAI', 'Fundamental Rights', 'My ALTAIs', 'Hello nathan.lea@i-hd.eu!', and 'Logout'. The main heading is 'ALTAI for GenoMed4All ALTAI Assessment'. A 'Notes' button is visible. The left sidebar lists sections: Human Agency and Oversight, Technical Robustness and Safety, Privacy and Data Governance (selected), Transparency, Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness, Societal and Environmental Well-being, and Accountability. Below the sidebar is a 'Legend of progression symbols' with three items: Unanswered, Partially filled, and Completed and validated. The 'Resources' section includes 'Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI'. The 'See the results' section has a 'Results and Recommendations' button. The main content area is titled 'Privacy and Data Governance' and contains a descriptive paragraph: 'Closely linked to the principle of prevention of harm is privacy, a fundamental right particularly affected by AI systems. Prevention of harm to privacy also necessitates adequate data governance that covers the quality and integrity of the data used, its relevance in light of the domain in which the AI systems will be deployed, its access protocols and the capability to process data in a manner that protects privacy.' Below this are three question boxes. The first asks: 'Did you consider the impact of the AI system on the right to privacy, the right to physical, mental and/or moral integrity and the right to data protection?' with radio buttons for Yes, No, and Don't know. The second asks: 'Depending on the use case, did you establish mechanisms that allow flagging issues related to privacy or data protection concerning the AI system?' with radio buttons for Yes and No. The third asks: 'Is your AI system being trained, or was it developed, by using or processing personal data (including special categories of personal data)?' with radio buttons for Yes, To some extent, No, and Don't know. A fourth question box asks: 'Did you put in place any of the following measures to thoroughly implement the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), or non-European equivalent?' with a list of five checked items: Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), Designate a Data Protection Officer (DPO), Oversight mechanisms for data processing, Measures to enhance privacy by design and default, and Data minimisation.

Figure 6: Privacy and Data Governance Altai Responses (Page 1)

Did you implement the right to withdraw consent, the right to object and the right to be forgotten in the **AI system**? *

Yes
 No

Did you consider the privacy and data protection implications of data collected, generated or processed over the course of the **AI system's lifecycle**? *

Yes
 No

Did you consider the privacy and data protection implications of the **AI system's non-personal training-data** or other processed non-personal data? *

Yes
 No

Did you align the **AI system** with relevant **standards** (e.g. ISO, IEEE) or widely adopted protocols for (daily) data management and **governance**? *

Yes
 No

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the privacy & **data governance** measures and procedures you have set up for the **AI system**? *

Non-existent Completely inadequate Almost adequate Adequate Fully adequate

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Figure 7: Privacy and Data Governance Altai Responses (Page 2)

4.4 Review of Responses to ALTAI Web Toolkit Requirement 4: Transparency

Figures 8 – 10 provide the ALTAI responses for Requirement 4.

The screenshot shows the ALTAI web toolkit interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Home', 'How To Complete The ALTAI', 'Fundamental Rights', 'My ALTAIs', 'Hello nathan.lea@i-hd.eu!', and 'Logout'. The main content area is titled 'ALTAI for GenoMed4All ALTAI Assessment' and includes a 'Notes' button and a 'Sections of the ALTAI' sidebar with categories like 'Human Agency and Oversight', 'Technical Robustness and Safety', 'Privacy and Data Governance', 'Transparency', 'Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness', 'Societal and Environmental Well-being', and 'Accountability'. The 'Transparency' section is active, displaying a definition of transparency and a list of response questions. The 'Traceability' section is also visible, defining its purpose. The 'Explainability' section includes a question about explaining decisions to users, a 'Please explain:' text area with a response, and a question about surveying users.

Transparency

A crucial component of achieving Trustworthy AI is transparency which encompasses three elements: 1) traceability, 2) explainability and 3) open communication about the limitations of the AI system. Technical robustness requires that AI systems be developed with a preventative approach to risks and in a manner such that they reliably behave as intended while minimising unintentional and unexpected harm, and preventing unacceptable harm. This should also apply to potential changes in their operating environment or the presence of other agents (human and artificial) that may interact with the system in an adversarial manner. In addition, the physical and mental integrity of humans should be ensured.

A crucial component of achieving Trustworthy AI is transparency which encompasses three elements: 1) traceability, 2) explainability and 3) open communication about the limitations of the AI system.

Traceability

This subsection helps to self-assess whether the processes of the development of the AI system, i.e. the data and processes that yield the AI systems decisions, is properly documented to allow for traceability, increase transparency and, ultimately, build trust in AI in society.

Did you put in place measures to continuously assess the quality of the input data to the AI system? *

- Yes
- To some extent
- No
- Don't know

Explainability

This subsection helps to self-assess the explainability of the AI system. The questions refer to the ability to explain both the technical processes of the AI system and the reasoning behind the decisions or predictions that the AI system makes. Explainability is crucial for building and maintaining users' trust in AI systems. AI driven decisions to the extent possible must be explained and understood to those directly and indirectly affected, in order to allow for contesting of such decisions. An explanation as to why a model has generated a particular output or decision (and what combination of input factors contributed to that) is not always possible. These cases are referred to as 'black boxes' and require special attention. In those circumstances, other explainability measures (e.g. traceability, auditability and transparent communication on the AI system capabilities) may be required, provided that the AI system as a whole respects fundamental rights. The degree to which explainability is needed depends on the context and the severity of the consequences of erroneous or otherwise inaccurate output to human lives.

Did you explain the decision of the AI system to the users? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Please explain:

The models being generated and training tag tis underway has been explained got clinical partners who have validated the use and approaches taken.

Do you continuously survey the users to ask them whether they understand the decision(s) of the AI system? *

- Yes
- To some extent
- No
- Don't know

Figure 8: Transparency ALTAI Responses (Page 1)

Communication

This subsection helps to self-assess whether the AI system's capabilities and limitations have been communicated to the users in a manner appropriate to the use case at hand. This could encompass communication of the AI system's level of accuracy as well as its limitations.

In cases of interactive AI systems (e.g., chatbots, robo-lawyers), do you communicate to users that they are interacting with an AI system instead of a human? *

- Yes
- To some extent
- No
- Don't know

Did you establish mechanisms to inform users about the purpose, criteria and limitations of the decision(s) generated by the AI system? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

Please explain:

The use of the tooling for risk prediction is very clearly identified as an AI tool for medico-legal reasons.

Did you communicate the technical limitations and potential risks of the AI system to end-users, such as its level of accuracy and/or error rates? *

- Yes
- No
- To some extent
- Don't know

Please explain:

The limitations are established by means of providing details of data issues and transparency around the completeness and quality of data. This will be further enhanced at any clinical trial that develops.

Figure 9: Transparency ALTAI Responses (Page 2)

Did you provide appropriate training material and disclaimers to users on how to adequately use the AI system? *

Yes
 No
 Don't know

Please explain:

This is part of the collaborative approach and will be used to formulate trial approaches.

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the measures you have adopted to ensure transparency? *

Non-existent Completely inadequate Almost adequate Adequate Fully adequate

Submit

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Figure 10: Transparency ALTAI Responses (Page 3)

GenoMed4All notes that transparency in terms of the ALTAI however focuses on traceability, explainability and communication. Whilst measures have been put in place to achieve these for the tooling, the traceability elements tally with the robustness requirements around data use.

Looking at transparency for AI systems holistically, this is inextricably linked to the ethical considerations and independent review – participants cannot meaningfully engage with the project if they are not equipped to consider the AI tooling, which relies on explainability for them. In formulating a response to Transparency, GenoMed4All includes both the functioning of the AI, communications to its users but also the understanding and informed consent of the data subjects who have contributed their data and may not themselves enjoy any benefit from the algorithms as the solutions are developed.

4.5 Review of Responses to ALTAI Web Toolkit Requirement 5: Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness

Please see Figures 11 – 16 for the ALTAI responses to Requirement 5.

The screenshot shows the ALTAI web toolkit interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, How To Complete The ALTAI, Fundamental Rights, My ALTAIs (highlighted), Hello nathan.lea@i-hd.eu, and Logout. The main content area is titled 'ALTAI for GenoMed4All ALTAI Assessment' and includes a 'Notes' button. A sidebar on the left lists sections of the ALTAI assessment, with 'Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness' selected. The main content area displays the title 'Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness' followed by a paragraph explaining the importance of inclusion and diversity in AI systems. Below this, there are four assessment questions, each with radio button options for Yes, No, or Not applicable. The questions are: 1. 'Did you establish a strategy or a set of procedures to avoid creating or reinforcing unfair bias in the AI system, both regarding the use of input data as well as for the algorithm design?' (Yes/No). 2. 'Did you consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and/or subjects in the data?' (Yes/No). 3. 'Did you test for specific target groups or problematic use case?' (Yes/No/Not applicable). 4. 'Did you research and use publicly available technical tools, that are state-of-the-art, to improve your understanding of the data, model and performance?' (Yes/No).

ALTAI for GenoMed4All ALTAI Assessment

Notes

Sections of the ALTAI

- Human Agency and Oversight
- Technical Robustness and Safety
- Privacy and Data Governance
- Transparency
- Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness**
- Societal and Environmental Well-being
- Accountability

Legend of progression symbols

- Unanswered
- Partially filled
- Completed and validated

Resources

[Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI](#)

See the results

Results and Recommendations

Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness

In order to achieve Trustworthy AI, we must enable inclusion and diversity throughout the entire AI system's life cycle. AI systems (both for training and operation) may suffer from the inclusion of inadvertent historic bias, incompleteness, and bad governance models. The continuation of such biases could lead to unintended (in)direct prejudice and discrimination against certain groups or people, potentially exacerbating prejudice and marginalisation. Harm can also result from the intentional exploitation of (consumer) biases or by engaging in unfair competition, such as the homogenisation of prices by means of collusion or a non-transparent market. Identifiable and discriminatory bias should be removed in the collection phase where possible. AI systems should be user-centric and designed in a way that allows all people to use AI products or services, regardless of their age, gender, abilities or characteristics. Accessibility to this technology for persons with disabilities, which are present in all societal groups, is of particular importance.

Avoidance of unfair bias

Did you establish a strategy or a set of procedures to avoid creating or reinforcing **unfair bias** in the **AI system**, both regarding the use of input data as well as for the algorithm design? ⓘ *

Yes
 No

Did you consider diversity and representativeness of **end-users** and/or **subjects** in the data? ⓘ *

Yes
 No

Did you test for specific target groups or problematic **use case**? ⓘ *

Yes
 No
 Not applicable

Did you research and use publicly available technical tools, that are state-of-the-art, to improve your understanding of the data, model and performance? ⓘ *

Yes
 No

Figure 11: Responses to ALTAI Requirement 5 - Discrimination and Fairness (Page 1)

Where relevant, did you consider diversity and representativeness of **end-users** and or **subjects** in the data? *

- Yes
- No

Did you put in place educational and awareness initiatives to help **AI designers** and **AI developers** be more aware of the possible **bias** they can inject in designing and developing the **AI system**? *

- Yes
- To some extent
- No

Depending on the **use case**, did you ensure a mechanism that allows for the flagging of issues related to **bias**, discrimination or poor performance of the **AI system**? *

- Yes
- No

Did you establish clear steps and ways of communicating on how and to whom such issues can be raised? *

- Yes
- No

Did you identify the **subjects** that could potentially be (in)directly affected by the **AI system**, in addition to the **end-users**? *

- Yes
- No

Figure 12: Responses to ALTAI Requirement 5 - Discrimination and Fairness (Page 2)

Is your definition of **fairness** commonly used and implemented in any phase of the process of setting up the **AI system**? *

Yes
 No

Please explain your definition of **fairness**:

Fairness of the recommendations and risk prediction results, ensuring that the disease conditions are adequately represented (o there they are not, this is clearly articulated), balancing of equity and autonomy to ensure that data completeness in rare conditions is not unduly compromised by the denying access to data since a federated model is being used and limiting risks to personal privacy.

Did you consider other definitions of **fairness** before choosing this one? *

Yes
 No

Did you consult with the impacted communities about the correct definition of **fairness**, i.e., representatives of elderly persons or persons with disabilities? *

Yes
 No

Did you ensure a quantitative analysis or metrics to measure and test the applied definition of **fairness**? *

Yes
 No

Did you establish mechanisms to ensure **fairness** in your **AI system**? *

Yes
 No

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the measures you have adopted to detect and avoid **bias**, and ensure **fairness**? *

Non-existent Completely inadequate Almost adequate Adequate Fully adequate

Figure 13: Responses to ALTAI Requirement 5 - Discrimination and Fairness (Page 3)

Accessibility and universal design

Particularly in business-to-consumer domains, AI systems should be user-centric and designed in a way that allows all people to use AI products or services, regardless of their age, gender, abilities or characteristics. Accessibility to this technology for persons with disabilities, which are present in all societal groups, is of particular importance. AI systems should not have a one-size-fits-all approach and should consider Universal Design principles addressing the widest possible range of users, following relevant accessibility standards. This will enable equitable access and active participation of all people in existing and emerging computer-mediated human activities and with regard to assistive technologies.

Did you ensure that the **AI system** corresponds to the variety of preferences and abilities in society? *

- Yes
- No

Did you assess whether the **AI system's** user interface is usable by those with special needs or disabilities or those at risk of exclusion? *

- Yes
- No

Did you ensure that **Universal Design** principles are taken into account during every step of the planning and development process, if applicable? *

- Yes
- No

Did you take the impact of the **AI system** on the potential **end-users** and/or **subjects** into account? *

- Yes
- No

Did you assess whether the team involved in building the **AI system** engaged with the possible target **end-users** and/or **subjects**? *

- Yes
- No

Figure 14: Responses to ALTAI Requirement 5 - Discrimination and Fairness (Page 4)

Did you assess whether there could be groups who might be disproportionately affected by the outcomes of the system? *

Yes
 No

Please explain::

This is an area of consideration addressed in the research protocols and informed consent procedures. This is also addressed in considering the limitations of the system and the human oversight of the recommendations.

Did you assess the risk of the possible **unfairness of the system onto the **end-users'** or **subjects'** communities? ***

Yes
 No

Please explain:

Consideration of the small cohort and rareness of the diseases so that equity can be established.

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the measures you implemented to ensure **accessibility and **Universal Design**? ***

Non-existent Completely inadequate Almost adequate Adequate Fully adequate

Figure 15: Responses to ALTAI Requirement 5 - Discrimination and Fairness (Page 5)

Stakeholder participation

In order to develop Trustworthy AI, it is advisable to consult stakeholders who may directly or indirectly be affected by the AI system throughout its life cycle. It is beneficial to solicit regular feedback even after deployment and set up longer term mechanisms for stakeholder participation, for example by ensuring workers information, consultation and participation throughout the whole process of implementing AI systems at organisations.

Did you consider a mechanism to include the participation of the widest range of possible stakeholders in the AI system's design and development?[?]

*

- Yes
 No

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the measures you put in place to ensure the involvement of the relevant stakeholders? *

- Non-existent Completely inadequate Almost adequate Adequate Fully adequate

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Figure 16: Responses to ALTAI Requirement 5 - Discrimination and Fairness (Page 6)

The responses to this requirement in the ALTAI were reasonably assured given that GenoMed4All is focused on rare diseases and those that impact a specific demographic. The risks were higher here in terms of assurance given that the data availability is very limited and that the development and use of the algorithms would therefore need to be very carefully assessed.

To that end, GenoMed4All feels that the limitations and potential to impact diversity, discrimination and fairness of generated algorithms should be better assessed in the context of a clinical trial where these points can be better understood.

The articulation of ensuring that data is available, and representative must also be prioritised. Stakeholder participation is discussed in more detail in section 6.

4.6 Review of Responses to ALTAI Web Toolkit for Requirement 6: Environmental and Societal Well-Being

Please see Figures 17 – 19 for the ALTAI responses to Requirement 6.

ALTAI for GenoMed4All
ALTAI Assessment

Sections of the ALTAI

- Human Agency and Oversight
- Technical Robustness and Safety
- Privacy and Data Governance
- Transparency
- Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness
- Societal and Environmental Well-being**
- Accountability

Legend of progression symbols

- Unanswered
- Partially filled
- Completed and validated

Resources

[Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI](#)

See the results

Results and Recommendations

Societal and Environmental Wellbeing

In line with the principles of fairness and prevention of harm, the broader society, other sentient beings and the environment should be considered as stakeholders throughout the AI system's life cycle. Ubiquitous exposure to social AI systems in all areas of our lives (be it in education, work, care or entertainment) may alter our conception of social agency, or negatively impact our social relationships and attachment. While AI systems can be used to enhance social skills, they can equally contribute to their deterioration. This could equally affect peoples' physical and mental well-being. The effects of AI systems must therefore be carefully monitored and considered. Sustainability and ecological responsibility of AI systems should be encouraged, and research should be fostered into AI solutions addressing areas of global concern, for instance the Sustainable Development Goals. Overall, AI should be used to benefit all human beings, including future generations. AI systems should serve to maintain and foster democratic processes and respect the plurality of values and life choices of individuals. AI systems must not undermine democratic processes, human deliberation or democratic voting systems or pose a systemic threat to society at large.

Environmental Wellbeing

This subsection helps to self-assess the (potential) positive and negative impacts of the AI system on the environment. AI systems, even if they promise to help tackle some of the most pressing societal concerns, e.g. climate change, must work in the most environmentally friendly way possible. The AI system's development, deployment and use process, as well as its entire supply chain, should be assessed in this regard (e.g. via a critical examination of the resource usage and energy consumption during training, opting for less net negative choices). Measures to secure the environmental friendliness of an AI system's entire supply chain should be encouraged.

Are there potential negative impacts of the AI system on the environment? *

Yes
 To some extent
 No
 Don't know

Which potential impact(s) do you identify?

Use of power to run High Performance Computing facilities.

Where possible, did you establish mechanisms to evaluate the environmental impact of the AI system's development, deployment and/or use (for example amount of energy used and carbon emissions)? *

Yes
 No

Did you define measures to reduce the environmental impact of the AI system throughout its lifecycle? *

Yes
 No

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the risk that the AI system negatively affects the environment? *

Non-existent
 Completely inadequate
 Almost adequate
 Adequate
 Fully adequate

How would you rate the measures you have adopted to mitigate this risk? *

Non-existent
 Completely inadequate
 Almost adequate
 Adequate
 Fully adequate

Figure 17: ALTAI Responses to Environmental and Societal Wellbeing (Page 1)

Impact on work and skills

AI systems may fundamentally alter the work sphere. They should support humans in the working environment, and aim for the creation of meaningful work. This subsection helps self-assess the impact of the AI system and its use in a working environment on workers, the relationship between workers and employers, and on skills.

Does the **AI system** impact human work and work arrangements? *

- Yes
- To some extent
- No
- Don't know

Did you pave the way for the introduction of the **AI system** in your organisation by informing and consulting with impacted workers and their representatives (trade unions, (European) work councils) in advance? *

- Yes
- No

Did you adopt measures to ensure that the work impacts of the **AI system** are well understood? *

- Yes
- No

How?

Partly by modelling the use of the system theoretically but also this would form a basis of assessment in a clinical trial.

Figure 18: ALTAI Responses to Environmental and Societal Wellbeing (Page 2)

Could the **AI system** create the risk of de-skilling of the workforce?[?] *

- Yes
- No

Did you provide training opportunities and materials for re- and up-skilling measures? *

- Yes
- No

Based on your answers to the previous questions, how would you rate the risk that the **AI system** negatively impacts work and work arrangements? *

- Non-existent
- Completely Inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

How would you rate the measures you have adopted to mitigate this risk? *

- Non-existent
- Completely Inadequate
- Almost adequate
- Adequate
- Fully adequate

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Figure 19: ALTAI Responses to Environmental and Societal Wellbeing (Page 3)

As a health data innovation project comprising multiple partners, the assessment of environmental impacts of the AI system and its supply chain provides a particularly challenging matter to assess. Arguably GenoMed4All and its partners are unable to collectively assess this and the societal impacts. Nevertheless some partners have described their operational specifics and are working within their own framework on an institutional level. We propose that this forms part of a separate piece of further work based on some of the specifications that have already been shared as part of the project.

With regards the wider societal impacts, GenoMed4All in developing tooling to support human activity with regards risk prediction and diagnostics. To that end it has been relatively simple to respond to the ALTAI in this regard as the scoping and reach of the tooling has been well defined

and constrained. Further consideration should be given to this in a trials setting as this may not yet be entirely defined in terms of the interventional aspect of the tool.

4.7 Review of Responses to ALTAI Web Toolkit for Requirement 7: Accountability

Please see Figures 20 – 22 for the Requirement 7 ALTAI responses.

The screenshot shows the ALTAI web toolkit interface. At the top is a navigation bar with links for Home, How To Complete The ALTAI, Fundamental Rights, My ALTAIs (highlighted), Hello nathan.lea@i-hd.eu!, and Logout. The main heading is 'ALTAI for GenoMed4All ALTAI Assessment'. Below this is a 'Notes' button and a list of 'Sections of the ALTAI' including Human Agency and Oversight, Technical Robustness and Safety, Privacy and Data Governance, Transparency, Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness, Societal and Environmental Well-being, and Accountability (checked). A 'Legend of progression symbols' shows Unanswered, Partially filled, and Completed and validated. There are 'Resources' and a 'See the results' section with a 'Results and Recommendations' button. The 'Accountability' section is highlighted in a grey box and contains the text: 'The principle of accountability necessitates that mechanisms be put in place to ensure responsibility for the development, deployment and/or use of AI systems. This topic is closely related to risk management, identifying and mitigating risks in a transparent way that can be explained to and audited by third parties. When unjust or adverse impacts occur, accessible mechanisms for accountability should be in place that ensure an adequate possibility of redress.' Below this is the 'Auditability' section, which explains that it helps self-assess the existing or necessary level for an evaluation of the AI system by internal and external auditors. It includes three questions in blue-bordered boxes: 1. 'Did you establish mechanisms that facilitate the AI system's auditability (e.g. traceability of the development process, the sourcing of training data and the logging of the AI system's processes, outcomes, positive and negative impact)?' with radio buttons for Yes, No, and Don't know. 2. 'Did you ensure that the AI system can be audited by independent third parties?' with radio buttons for Yes, No, and Don't know. 3. 'Based on the answer you gave above, do you believe the measures in place to ensure the auditability of the AI system are?' with radio buttons for Non-existent, Completely Inadequate, Almost adequate, Adequate (selected), and Fully adequate.

Figure 20: ALTAI Responses for Accountability (Page 1)

Risk Management

Both the ability to report on actions or decisions that contribute to the AI system's outcome, and to respond to the consequences of such an outcome, must be ensured. Identifying, assessing, documenting and minimising the potential negative impacts of AI systems is especially crucial for those (in)directly affected. Due protection must be available for whistle-blowers, NGOs, trade unions or other entities when reporting legitimate concerns about an AI system. When implementing the above requirements, tensions may arise between them, which may lead to inevitable trade-offs. Such trade-offs should be addressed in a rational and methodological manner within the state of the art. This entails that relevant interests and values implicated by the AI system should be identified and that, if conflict arises, trade-offs should be explicitly acknowledged and evaluated in terms of their risk to safety and ethical principles, including fundamental rights. Any decision about which trade-off to make should be well reasoned and properly documented. When adverse impact occurs, accessible mechanisms should be foreseen that ensure adequate redress.

General Awareness

Did you foresee any kind of external guidance or third-party auditing processes to oversee ethical concerns and accountability measures? *

Yes
 No
 Don't know

Does the involvement of these third parties go beyond the development phase? *

Yes
 No
 Don't know

Did you organise risk training and, if so, does this also inform about the potential legal framework applicable to the AI system? *

Yes
 No
 Don't know

Did you consider establishing an 'AI ethics review board' or a similar mechanism to discuss the overall accountability and ethics practices, including potential unclear grey areas? *

Yes
 No
 Don't know

Figure 21: ALTAI Responses for Accountability (Page 2)

Possible conflicts of interests and values

Did you establish a mechanism to identify conflicts of values that could be implemented in your AI system and your own interests? *

Yes
 No
 Don't know

Does this process include identification and documentation of trade-offs between different ethical principles? ⓘ *

Yes
 No
 Don't know

How did you decide on such trade-offs? Did you ensure that the trade-off decision was documented? ⓘ *

Yes
 No
 Don't know

Did you establish a processes for third parties (e.g. suppliers, end-users, subjects, distributors/vendors or workers) or workers to report potential vulnerabilities, risks or biases in the AI system? ⓘ *

Yes
 No
 Don't know

Does this process foster revision of the risk management process? ⓘ *

Yes
 No
 Don't know

For applications that can significantly adversely affect individuals, have redress by design mechanisms been put in place? ⓘ *

Yes
 No
 Don't know

Based on the answer you gave above, do you believe the risk management system you have in place is: *

Non-existent Completely Inadequate Almost adequate Adequate Fully adequate

This website is a prototype of an interactive version of the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI. We encourage you not to use personal information or intellectual property while using this website. Full details of how we process personal data and your rights under Data Protection legislation are set out in our [Privacy Statement](#).

Figure 22: ALTAI Responses for Accountability (Page 3)

The ethical review processes and the conflict of value assessments also is embedded in the risk management processes described throughout WP2 and WP10 and its deliverables. This includes risk management and ethical conflict resolution as per the EAB's role.

The overriding ethical principle with regards accountability remains that this relies on very well established accountability mechanisms as specified by GDPR's Data Protection by Design and Default approach, research governance requirements around ethical and safety reviews, as well as the HTA and Medical Device Regulation aspects. These must and should be leveraged to provide a foundation to the ability of any commissioner, regulator or research group to assess the development of an AI driven system as well as the operation of the AI components.

5 Ethical Principles, Quality Processes, Stakeholder Engagements and Discussion

In this section the recommendations for ethical principles are provided. Each subsection relates a set of principles to each of the seven key ALTAI requirements. A review of the engagement strategy for each of the key stakeholder groups follows the ethical principles, and recommendations for quality assurances are described. This section concludes with a discussion of the limitations of the approach taken. The discussion also considers the likely implications of the AI Act and how the challenges GenoMed4All has addressed in anticipation of the AI Act enactment can be better asserted in compliance with the likely final draft of the Regulation.

5.1 Recommended Ethical Principles

5.1.1 Ethical Principles Derived from Human Agency and Oversight

1.1 All stakeholders should be identified early in an AI driven intervention so that their agency and oversight expectations can be understood;

1.2 Agency and oversight interpretations across stakeholders will differ and should be addressed openly and clearly;

1.3 Practical assertion of agency and oversight will be different across the stakeholder groups and must be assessed and honoured in a meaningful and effective manner for each group;

1.4 Any trial or assessment design must emphasise a full consideration of reliance on AI, user manipulation and the extent of human agency and ability to override decisions or recommendations.

5.1.2 Ethical Principles Derived from Technical Robustness and Safety

2.1 All data processing components must be mapped and described in detail so that their operation can be easily replicated, effectively repaired and transparently explained to stakeholders;

2.2 System setups for AI driven services should be readily isolated so that no live clinical or research systems are compromised in the event of a failure using AI technologies that may be difficult or unaffordable to replicate.

2.3 Partners involved in data processing must be prepared to be internally or externally audited against contractual agreements around information security and particulars of assessment frameworks such as the ALTAI;

2.4 Agreements must be binding and provide a basis to require basic information security management to assure system robustness and safety.

2.5 The operation of the algorithms must be explainable and transparent to assure their accurate results generation where this assurance is unattainable if the quality of the training data cannot itself be assured in the first instance.

5.1.3 Ethical Principles Derived from Privacy and Governance

3.1 All stakeholders must accept that any data processing model, whether federated or centralised, will involve data processing regardless of whether data is sent to recipients or recipients process data remotely, and will likely hold a Joint Controller or Processor role regardless of whether the data is sent to their infrastructure;

3.2 When assessing the data processing needs for machine learning and AI, developers, researchers and clinical teams must all carefully consider the need to review the data and whether they need site of it, or whether it can remain in the control of the data providers to enhance privacy under a Federated Model or Health Data Space model;

3.3 In processing data for AI development, stakeholders should assume that they take responsibility for that processing and ensure this is clearly established in contract and privacy notices where contracts and privacy notices shall not be overly complicated, and the processing needs are clearly established in particulars of processing;

3.4 All stakeholders must assume that a personal data and privacy enhancing model is at play from the outset so that the governance model can be asserted to a high degree of privacy protection and sound, ethical data processing practice.

5.1.4 Ethical Principles Derived from Transparency

4.1 All transparency materials must be independently reviewed by research ethics committees and review boards to ensure clarity and high standards of research participation transfer to transparency on how AI has been trained and operates;

4.2 Mindful that ethical oversight varies between different committees and different nations, consistency must be achieved on the transparency materials provided to research participants and in the case of direct interventions on care services, patients and the wider citizenry;

4.3 Transparency materials must be reviewed by patient representatives or associations to ensure a clear picture considering their experiences, needs and expectations.

4.4 Transparency must be achieved in a testable and meaningful manner – reuse of the standards set by GDPR is necessary and will assist with consistency within a properly risk managed framework;

4.5 Transparency is a means for citizens to form a view on whether they feel that AI is equitable for them and their peers but cannot be meaningful if AI use based on their records and experiences is underway without their knowledge or say so. Transparency materials must therefore be agreed prior to training of any algorithms where this also effects other stakeholders like treating clinicians and care services.

4.6 The traceability, explainability and communication around the AI tooling must prioritise data subject contributions in addition to the users of the systems and the patients and participants benefiting from

5.1.5 Ethical Principles Derived from Diversity, Non-Discrimination and Fairness

5.1 In balancing risks to access and equity, ensure that the context of AI training and use is fully understood so as not to discriminate against a vulnerable cohort in being overly cautious in data processing;

5.2 Ethics committees must be expected to ensure consistency across deliberations where this is an important consideration for researchers and sites to adequately engage with the ethics committees as needed in multinational collaborations.

5.1.6 Ethical Principles Derived from Environmental and Societal Well-Being

6.1 In supplying components for AI tooling development (including training data), developers must refer to procurement strategies and institutional policies on environmental impact;

6.2 AI tooling used for care and diagnostic purposes must be fully scoped in terms of mode and manner of the intervention and trialled accordingly to ascertain the risk of damaging the human activity and benefit for patients and health professionals, as well as any detriments.

5.1.7 Ethical Principles Derived from Accountability

7.1 Ensure that the scope and specification of the AI components of a system can reach the same level of accountability that already exist for data use and the conduct of research.

5.2 Stakeholder Engagement and Quality Processes

For each of the Stakeholders outlined in Section 2, there are specific considerations to be aware of with regards their engagement. This is documented in Table 1 as follows. The table provides

an indication of the focus of each of the ALTAI Requirements for each stakeholder groups, and the recommendations around their engagement and their roles.

Stakeholder	ALTAI Focus	Engagement Recommendations
Clinical Researchers and Practitioners (Haematological Diseases)	All	It is vital to ensure that this stakeholder group is engaged throughout the development, testing and use cycle; they must be clear on the operation of the system, lead the interpretation of findings and validate the models generated as well as predictions and diagnostics that are provided.
Infrastructure Operators	Technical Robustness and Security, Environment, Accountability	They must be sufficiently funded and instructed to provide secure and robust software and hardware services in line with regulatory requirements and other stakeholder protections around service provision, timeliness of access and privacy, security and transparency
Technical Expertise: Data Scientists, Designers, Analysts and Developers for algorithm training and software services	All	They must be encouraged and clear on the need to ensure transparency and traceability of results as well as development of tooling and generation and implementation of models
Programme Managers and Internal Oversight	Technical Robustness and Security, Privacy and Data Governance, Accountability	They must be enabled to understand the processes and progress of all development and implementation steps; they must be able to oversee and assess progress and provide

		guidance on addressing ethical, legal and technical challenges that arise
Regulators and Commissioners	All	They must be kept up to date as to progress of tooling as well as how regulations and oversight are working with regards model development.
Patients, Research Participants and the Wider Citizenry	All	They must be engaged in a meaningful manner where they are generally better equipped and informed about current issues with new technology and policy. All ALTAI considerations have a direct impact on this group, and it is important for AI users and developers to remember the contribution of the citizenry where the honest position is that data about individuals will likely benefit others via AI but not necessarily the data subject whose data has been used to develop the tools

Table 1: Stakeholder Engagement Recommendations

5.3 Discussion

In considering ethical principles, quality processes and stakeholder engagements for a complex project like GenoMed4All, it is vital to ensure that a widely developed series of assessments and criteria can be used to provide some assurance that the key concerns around the use of AI have been addressed.

Some of the more practical elements will be addressed by the AI Act – at least in the case of high-risk systems. The AI Act imposes requirements of competent authority oversight and certification and encourages the adherence for low and medium risk systems as well.

The AI Act also specifies the requirement for what elements it governs, which is why the AI components themselves need to be clearly defined in terms of their operational scope so that each part of a given intervention can be appropriately assessed under the regulatory frameworks to which they are applicable. This may also include the Medical Device Regulation, Health Technology Assessments, information security and wider data protection certification as well as standards associated with the forthcoming EHDS regulations.

This is where the ALTAI has proven useful – it is a well prepared series of criteria that has been developed off a wide consultation and analyses of ethical issues challenges by AI and is a basis to operationalise some of the risk management associated with AI.

This has required GenoMed4All in this case to interpret and associate the ALTAI assessment with the wider risk management process that has been underway since the project commenced.

A main limitation of the approach that GenoMed4All has taken, and the findings of this Deliverable is that it is strictly speaking a self assessment. A formal certification scheme such as ISO 27001 certification would require an independent auditor to assess a service, device or institution. The AI Act would seem to indicate strongly that independent assessments are required for AI components in a high risk system.

The situation therefore strongly indicates that the findings in this report should take the approach and the assessment as a stepping stone for what is likely to follow under a new regulatory framework. Additionally, there are more formal approaches that GenoMed4All could take in the remaining time to offer assurances around governance and robustness compliance. To that end it may be the case that these assessments can be run moving forward from WP2 colleagues using an existing assurance framework like the IDHIS approach developed by i~HD⁵.

As part of a future sustainability drive, the testing of GenoMed4All outputs will need to be considered as part of a pre-clinical trial most likely, In the case of the assessments, each of the ALTAI requirements will need to be assessed in this context. The specific points of engagement are listed in the responses throughout Section 4. With regards agency, oversight, impact, traceability and transparency as well as concerns around discrimination and prejudice, only an assessment in a trial setting will give the assurance needed for GenoMed4All's solutions.

⁵ <https://www.i-hd.eu/idhis-information-governance-certification-programme/>

6 Conclusions

The field of AI in the context of health data innovation is nascent in terms of its impact, outreach and utility within the context of intervention. With the drive across the EU and EEA to allow citizens to assert their rights over data that has been recorded about them in all contexts, including health, the anxieties around AI driven interventions suggest that the nature of that control as well as that of their care teams is being ceded to not only compute intensive algorithmic processes, but those who hold licence over the operation and ownership of those algorithms.

This is why the experience of projects like GenoMed4All are so important. Not only do they hold themselves to the highest of standards in terms of research integrity, participant involvement and clinical decision making, but they also provide a basis upon which to fully understand the implications of making sure that AI driven solutions operate under existing and forthcoming regulations.

This Deliverable has been drafted to ensure that the learning of GenoMed4All is fully and that its experience of governing early AI driven intervention can be reused by other innovation activities, but also form the basis of timely and effective intervention that can be measured in a trials setting and / or ensure that equity can be honoured for all stakeholders in health discovery and data driven innovation. Next steps in terms of operationalising these recommendations would be specifically around the conduct of a trial informed by the issues and challenges described in this deliverable as per the ALTAI Assessment.

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